
Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Afrina Yenni¹, Sabri², Aulia Fauziah³, Merry Luciana⁴, Dian Destria⁵

^{1,3,4,5} Master of Management Program, Public Policy Department, Haji Agus Salim Institute of Technology and Business, Bukittinggi, West Sumatra

²Lecturer at the Haji Agus Salim Institute of Technology and Business, Bukittinggi, West Sumatra, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The objective of this study is to identify and analyze the factors that influence the quality of public services at the Public Service Mall in Bukittinggi City. The population in this research includes all members of the public who used Public Service Mall services during the period from January to December 2024, totaling 44,793 individuals. The sample consisted of 150 respondents, determined using the approach of five respondents per indicator (30 indicators × 5). Data were collected through the distribution of questionnaires using a Likert scale, which had previously been tested for validity and reliability. The analytical technique used in this study was multiple linear regression. The results of the study show that the five independent variables (budget availability, technology utilization, infrastructure condition, changes in policies and regulations, and the competence and professionalism of human resources) have a positive and significant influence on the quality of public services, both partially and simultaneously. Thus, these five factors are important determinants in achieving high-quality public service delivery at the Public Service Mall in Bukittinggi City.

KEYWORDS: Public Service Quality, Budget Availability, Technology Utilization, Infrastructure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of forming a government is to create order and comfort that allows people to live a decent life. The government plays an important role in providing services to the community and creating conditions conducive to the implementation of the principle of justice, so that every citizen can receive services in accordance with the mandate stated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

Based on Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009, public service is defined as an activity or series of activities carried out by service providers to meet the public's needs for goods, services, and/or administrative services. This law also establishes the rights and obligations of agencies or institutions that provide public services, and regulates the relationship between the public as service recipients and the providers as service providers. These provisions are binding and serve as the legal basis for the implementation of public services in Indonesia (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009).

Public service providers are required to act fairly without discrimination, work with precision, and demonstrate a polite and friendly attitude so that the public feels valued and comfortable. Furthermore, they must be firm, reliable, and avoid making ambiguous or confusing decisions. (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009). One of the best ways to obtain high-quality public services is considered to be public service administration reform. In the effort to create good governance, public services become the driving force of administrative reform. This condition has led to changes in public desires regarding public service standards. The current government must prioritize a service system that is targeted, effective, and fast. One innovation pursued by the government, both at the national and regional levels, in order to improve the quality of public service delivery is through the establishment of Public Service Malls (MPP). This initiative allows the integration of various types of services from various agencies into one integrated location, which was previously difficult due to differences in authority between institutions. Referring to (Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 2017) concerning the Implementation of Public Service Malls, MPP is defined as a location that provides various types of public services, whether in the form of goods, services, or administration. MPP is a form of development of an integrated service system that has previously been implemented at the central and regional levels, and includes collaborative services from government agencies,

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

BUMN, BUMD, to the private sector. The purpose of implementing MPP is to provide services that are fast, easily accessible, affordable, safe, and comfortable for the community as service recipients.

In Indonesia, the integrated public service system began with the first generation, known as the One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSA). This system then evolved into the second generation, the One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSP), and then into the third generation, the Public Service Mall (MPP), which brings together various types of services in one location.

It is hoped that the Public Service Mall will become the third generation and can complement the function of the Integrated One-Stop Service without discontinuing existing services. In fact, the role of the Integrated One-Stop Service is increasingly developing as a driving force behind the establishment of the Public Service Mall. To strengthen the implementation of the Public Service Mall, the government issued Presidential Regulation Number 89 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the Public Service Mall. This regulation was issued as an effort to increase the effectiveness and optimize the operations of the existing MPP (Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 89 of 2021).

Public Service Malls (MPP) are facilities used to provide various types of public services, including the provision of goods, services, and administrative services. The presence of MPPs is the result of the development of the integrated service concept implemented at the national and regional levels, involving the roles of regionally-owned enterprises (BUMD) and the private sector. Public Service Malls (MPP) aim to provide fast, accessible, safe, and convenient services to the public. In addition to providing ease of access to public services, the existence of MPP also plays a role in encouraging ease of doing business in Indonesia, strengthening the implementation of excellent service standards by the government, and increasing national competitiveness at the global level. The existence of the Public Service Mall reflects the government's commitment to reforming Indonesia's public service system. This initiative aims to improve service quality, making it more efficient, affordable, and providing a sense of security and comfort for the public. Furthermore, the MPP is expected to facilitate doing business in Indonesia and serve as a strategic innovation in efforts to improve the quality of public services and community welfare.

As a form of implementation of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services, the Bukittinggi City Government has stipulated the Bukittinggi Mayor Regulation Number 28 of 2023. This regulation contains provisions regarding the delegation of authority for the implementation of business licensing, permits, and non-licensing services to the Head of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Agency (DPMPTSP (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 2009) . The establishment of the Public Service Mall (MPP) in Bukittinggi City is motivated by the Decree of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Number 11 of 2018 concerning the designation of 11 regions as locations for the implementation of MPP. In this decision, Bukittinggi City is included in the list of regions required to immediately establish MPP. The purpose of establishing this MPP is to provide services to the community that are fast, easy to reach, affordable, safe, and comfortable, as well as an effort to support increased national competitiveness.

Research conducted by Mustamin and his colleagues previously explored the influence of various factors on the quality of public services in village offices, such as the work motivation of apparatus and bureaucracy, apparatus capabilities, oversight mechanisms or social control, bureaucratic behavior, communication, and organizational restructuring efforts. Based on the results of the analysis using a Likert Scale and respondent assessments, it was found that the most significant factors in improving the quality of public services were organizational/apparatus behavior, work motivation, communication, village apparatus competence, and social supervision. However, several indicators still showed less than optimal contributions, such as in terms of organizational restructuring, the conceptual capabilities of village apparatus, the effectiveness of program supervision, and adjustments to the organizational structure that were not fully aligned with existing needs.

This is different from what happened at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. Providing services to the public is certainly inseparable from the support of several factors including internal, external, human, process and policy factors. One example of an internal factor is the availability of resources (financial, technological, and infrastructure). In terms of budget availability, the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall experiences obstacles in the form of insufficient budget provided for the operational costs of the Public Service Mall, where one of them is the lack of a budget for the procurement of generators, as it is known that generators are very necessary at the Public Service Mall because all service processes are carried out online using applications and will greatly disrupt services if there is a power outage. On the other hand, with budget limitations, the Public Service Mall has difficulty carrying out building maintenance, maintenance of facilities and infrastructure equipment and there is no budget to provide training to front office employees, customer service, security guards and cleaning services. In terms of technology utilization, the Public Service Mall has not implemented an online application-based queuing system. As a result, people who want to access services must first come directly to the location to get a queue number. For infrastructure, the Public Service Mall still needs to be repaired and reorganized, for example the location of the Samsat stand is far from the bank, so many visitors experience confusion when they want to make payment transactions to the bank, the absence of directional signs, causing visitors to also experience confusion, in addition to the parking area, there is no separation between employee parking and visitor parking, and the parking

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

is not neatly arranged between employee vehicles and visitor vehicles. There is no shelter for 2-wheeled vehicles, so that when it rains it causes the 2-wheeled vehicles to get wet.

Furthermore, changes in policies and regulations have impacted the service process, particularly since the enactment of Government Regulation Number 5 of 2021. This policy requires all licensing processes to be conducted online through digital applications. However, some visitors still experience difficulties accessing and understanding the application, which is generally caused by a lack of outreach activities to the public. Finally, the Competence and Professionalism of Human Resources factor can be seen from the security guard service not yet meeting the 3S service standards (smile, greet, say hello). Sometimes the information provided by the security guard is unclear, leaving visitors confused. There are several points in the Public Service Mall building that have not been thoroughly cleaned by cleaning staff, and there is still dust and small debris at several service locations. In addition, not all service personnel have received special training to support services such as sign language training, training
In an effort to achieve the goal of establishing a Public Service Mall (MPP), namely to provide fast, accessible, affordable, safe, and convenient services to the public. The Bukittinggi City Government chose to build the MPP in the city's central government area. In addition to being supported by adequate physical facilities, the Bukittinggi City MPP also implements a service system that welcomes all visitors, including people with disabilities and children. Public enthusiasm is evident in the high number of daily visits, especially for licensing and government administrative services.

The services provided at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall (MPP) under the management of the One-Stop Integrated Investment and Services Agency (DPMPTSP) have received a positive response from the public. In fact, this MPP has become a comparative study location for a number of regions, both from the West Sumatra Province and from outside the province. The Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall (MPP) collaborates with various institutions, including 17 vertical agencies and 6 Regional Work Units (SKPD) within the Bukittinggi City Government. This MPP consolidates various types of public services in one integrated location, so that the public does not need to move to access various services. Simply moving from one counter to another, the public can take care of different administrative needs practically. In line with the purpose of establishing the MPP which prioritizes fast, easily accessible, and convenient services for the public, the author felt motivated to conduct research with the title: "Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Service Theory

Referring to (Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 2003), public services are defined as all forms of services provided by the government, both in the form of goods and services, which aim to fulfill the needs of the community and implement the provisions contained in laws and regulations (Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 2003).

According to Haryanto (2015), service is defined as additional activities carried out outside of primary obligations, such as teaching activities, which are provided to service users as a form of appreciation and respect. Meanwhile, Moenir, AS (2016) states that public service is an activity carried out by individuals or groups, which involves material elements and is implemented based on certain systems, procedures, and methods to meet the needs of other parties in accordance with their inherent rights.

Principles of Public Service

Based on (Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 2003), in the implementation of public services, there are a number of fundamental principles that need to be applied as a reference in providing services to the community, namely:

1. Simplicity
The public service process flow must be designed to be concise, uncomplicated, and have a flow that is easy to understand.
2. Clarity
Public services must have clear technical and administrative requirements, including clarity regarding authorized officials, procedures for handling public complaints, and transparency in costs and payment process flows.
3. Certainty of Time
For Public Service Provision must be accompanied by a measurable completion time limit and in accordance with previously determined standards or provisions.
4. Accuracy
The service provided must be correct, on target, legally valid, and in accordance with the expectations of the service recipient.

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

5. Security

The implementation and output of public services should provide a sense of security and comfort to the public, thereby increasing trust in service providers.

6. Responsibility

There are parties or officials who are firmly responsible for implementing services and resolving every public complaint.

7. The availability of service facilities and infrastructure

Must be supported by adequate work facilities, including information technology, telecommunications, and other supporting infrastructure.

8. Ease of Access

The location of the service provider must be easily accessible to the public, strategic, and not difficult for service users.

9. Discipline, Politeness, and Friendliness

Public service apparatus are required to demonstrate disciplined behavior, politeness, friendliness, and carry out their duties with sincerity in order to create quality services.

10. environments

need to be designed to be orderly, clean, and supportive of public comfort. Facilities such as waiting rooms, parking areas, restrooms, places of worship, and access for people with disabilities must be available and adequate. (Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 2003) .

2. PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY INDICATORS

Parasuraman (2014) identified five main indicators in assessing the quality of public services, which include:

1. Reliability – reflects the agency's ability to provide services as promised consistently and accurately.
2. Responsiveness – describes the alertness and willingness of employees to help the public and provide services quickly.
3. Confidence – includes knowledge, politeness, and employee skills in building trust from service users.
4. Empathy – showing concern and personal attention given to the community as service recipients.
5. Physical evidence (Tangibles) – includes the physical condition of facilities and infrastructure, completeness of equipment, appearance of staff, and communication media used (Renyut 2023) .

This model is relevant for use as a measuring tool in evaluating the quality of public service performance provided by government institutions. In this regard, state officials have no reason to ignore public satisfaction, as this level of satisfaction can be an indicator of the success of a service. Therefore, the government needs to commit to providing services wholeheartedly as part of its responsibility (Ramdani 2020).

3. SERVQUAL MODEL

This model is one of the most widely used methods for measuring service quality. This approach consists of five main dimensions:

- a. Physical evidence (Tangibles): Refers to the physical condition of facilities, equipment, and the appearance of employees that reflect the professionalism of the service.
- b. Reliability: Describes the consistency and accuracy of the service provider in fulfilling the promises that have been made.
- c. Responsiveness: Refers to the willingness and speed of staff in assisting and providing services to users.
- d. Assurance: Demonstrating staff knowledge, friendly attitude, and ability to build customer security and trust in the service.
- e. Empathy: Relates to individual attention and concern of officers towards the needs and expectations of each service user.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

1. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative approach. A quantitative approach is a research method whose design has been systematically and structured from the beginning to the design stage (Hawing and Hartaman 2021) . The research location is the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. The research subjects are visitors who require services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

2. Population and Sample

A population is a collection of objects or subjects within a specific area that possess characteristics and distinctive features determined by the researcher as the primary focus of the study and serve as the basis for drawing research conclusions. Populations are not limited to humans but also include objects and other natural elements. Therefore, a population refers not

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

simply to the number of individuals but also encompasses all attributes or characteristics inherent in the objects or subjects being studied (Dinda Septiani and Sulistyawati 2022).

The population in this study included all residents who received services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall during the period from January to December 2024, with a total of 44,793 applicants who received services at the location. (Source: Bukittinggi City PMPTSP Service, 2024).

The sample in this study consisted of individuals who used services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. This study used accidental sampling, a sampling method that selects respondents who were encountered by chance and easily accessible to the researcher (Handayani 2020).

Accidental Sampling, according to Sugiyono (2016), is obtaining respondents to be used as samples based on chance, namely from people who meet the author by chance (Handayani 2020). This means that every individual encountered by the researcher can be used as a sample if they meet the main criteria as a service user at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

According to Hair, the recommended minimum sample size is between 5 and 10 respondents for each indicator analyzed. The reason for using a sample size that is not too large is because a sample size that is too large, such as 400 respondents, can cause the analysis method to be too sensitive, making it difficult to achieve an optimal goodness of fit value (Hooper, Coughlan, and Mullen 2008). Therefore, in this study involving 30 indicators, the minimum sample size was determined using the formula (number of indicators \times 5), so that a minimum of 150 respondents was obtained.

3. Operational Definition of Research

According to Sugiyono (2016), the operational definition of a variable in research is the attributes, characteristics, or values of an object or activity that vary, which have been determined by the researcher as the focus of the study and used as a reference in drawing research conclusions. Formulating a definition for each research variable is important to avoid errors in the data collection process. The operational definition of each variable in this study is outlined as follows:

Table 1: Operational Definition

Operational Definition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
1. Quality of Public Services (Y) The quality of public services is a state that continues to develop and includes aspects of products, services, human resources, processes, and the environment, where evaluation of this quality is carried out when services are provided to the public (Arifin Akbar 2018)	1. Reliability 2. Responsiveness 3. Confidence 4. Empathy 5. Tangible	Likert Scale 1 – 5
2. Budget Availability (X1) Budget availability is a critical factor in implementing regional autonomy, including financial stability and the availability of supporting facilities. Without an adequate budget, the implementation of public programs will be hampered (Kaho, 1997).	1. Planning 2. Implementation 3. Human Resources (HR) 4. Regulation	Likert Scale 1 – 5
3. Technology (X2) Technology in the context of Information Technology (IT) is understood as a set of methods and tools used by management to control change and produce something amidst the dynamics of change (Ndraha, 2003).	1. Efficiency and Effectiveness 2. Transparency and Accountability 3. Accessibility 4. Community Participation 5. Quality of Service	Likert Scale 1 – 5
4. Infrastructure (X3) Infrastructure is a key factor in determining the quality of public services (Hadi et al., 2021).	1. Availability 2. Accessibility 3. Quality 4. Utilization 5. Economic Impact	Likert Scale 1 – 5

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Operational Definition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
<p>5. Policy and Regulatory Changes (X4)</p> <p>According to Budi Winarno, policy changes can include the creation of new policies as well as improvements to existing policies.</p>	<p>1. Service Policy</p> <p>2. Human Resources Professionalism</p> <p>3. Facilities and infrastructure</p> <p>4. Service Information System</p> <p>5. Consultation and Complaints</p> <p>6. Service Innovation</p>	Likert Scale 1 – 5
<p>6. Human Resources Competence and Professionalism (X5)</p> <p>According to Spencer and Spencer, competence is defined as a fundamental characteristic that is inherent in an individual and directly influences success in carrying out a job or facing certain situations with superior performance. Meanwhile, Siagian explained that professionalism reflects the ability to carry out tasks effectively, produce high-quality output, be timely, accurate, and follow systematic procedures that are easy for service users to understand.</p>	<p>1. Self-development</p> <p>2. Loyalty or faithfulness</p> <p>3. Punctuality</p> <p>4. Ability</p> <p>5. Initiative</p>	Likert Scale 1 – 5

Source: Journals

4. MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

In this study, hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis processed using Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) software. The multiple linear regression method is used to determine the extent to which independent variables influence the dependent variable. The general form of the multiple linear regression equation used in this study is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

Where:

Y	=	Dependent Variable, Quality of Public Services
α	=	Intercept Constant
X1	=	Independent Variable, Budget Availability
X2	=	Independent Variable, Technology
X3	=	Control Variables, Infrastructure
X4	=	Control Variables, Policy Changes and Regulations
X5	=	Control Variables, Competence and Professionalism of Human Resources
$\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \beta_4 \beta_5$	=	Regression Coefficient
e	=	Term Error

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

1. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative approach. A quantitative approach is a research method whose design has been systematically and structured from the beginning to the design stage (Hawing and Hartaman 2021). The research location is the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. The research subjects are visitors who require services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

2. Population and Sample

A population is a collection of objects or subjects within a specific area that possess characteristics and distinctive features determined by the researcher as the primary focus of the study and serve as the basis for drawing research conclusions.

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Populations are not limited to humans but also include objects and other natural elements. Therefore, a population refers not simply to the number of individuals but also encompasses all attributes or characteristics inherent in the objects or subjects being studied (Dinda Septiani and Sulistyawati 2022).

The population in this study included all residents who received services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall during the period from January to December 2024, with a total of 44,793 applicants who received services at the location. (Source: Bukittinggi City PMPTSP Service, 2024).

The sample in this study consisted of individuals who used services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. This study used accidental sampling, a sampling method that selects respondents who were encountered by chance and easily accessible to the researcher (Handayani 2020).

Accidental Sampling, according to Sugiyono (2016), is obtaining respondents to be used as samples based on chance, namely from people who meet the author by chance (Handayani 2020). This means that every individual encountered by the researcher can be used as a sample if they meet the main criteria as a service user at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

According to Hair, the recommended minimum sample size is between 5 and 10 respondents for each indicator analyzed. The reason for using a sample size that is not too large is because a sample size that is too large, such as 400 respondents, can cause the analysis method to be too sensitive, making it difficult to achieve an optimal goodness of fit value (Hooper, Coughlan, and Mullen 2008). Therefore, in this study involving 30 indicators, the minimum sample size was determined using the formula (number of indicators \times 5), so that a minimum of 150 respondents was obtained.

3. Operational Definition of Research

According to Sugiyono (2016), the operational definition of a variable in research is the attributes, characteristics, or values of an object or activity that vary, which have been determined by the researcher as the focus of the study and used as a reference in drawing research conclusions. Formulating a definition for each research variable is important to avoid errors in the data collection process. The operational definition of each variable in this study is outlined as follows:

Table 2: Operational Definition

Operational Definition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
1. Quality of Public Services (Y) The quality of public services is a state that continues to develop and includes aspects of products, services, human resources, processes, and the environment, where evaluation of this quality is carried out when services are provided to the public (Arifin Akbar 2018)	1. Reliability 2. Responsiveness 3. Confidence 4. Empathy 5. Tangible	Likert Scale 1 – 5
2. Budget Availability (X1) Budget availability is a critical factor in implementing regional autonomy, including financial stability and the availability of supporting facilities. Without an adequate budget, the implementation of public programs will be hampered (Kaho, 1997).	1. Planning 2. Implementation 3. Human Resources (HR) 4. Regulation	Likert Scale 1 – 5
3. Technology (X2) Technology in the context of Information Technology (IT) is understood as a set of methods and tools used by management to control change and produce something amidst the dynamics of change (Ndraha, 2003).	1. Efficiency and Effectiveness 2. Transparency and Accountability 3. Accessibility 4. Community Participation 5. Quality of Service	Likert Scale 1 – 5
4. Infrastructure (X3) Infrastructure is a key factor in determining the quality of public services (Hadi et al., 2021).	1. Availability 2. Accessibility 3. Quality 4. Utilization 5. Economic Impact	Likert Scale 1 – 5

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Operational Definition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
<p>5. Policy and Regulatory Changes (X4) According to Budi Winarno, policy changes can include the creation of new policies as well as improvements to existing policies.</p>	<p>1. Service Policy 2. Human Resources Professionalism 3. Facilities and infrastructure 4. Service Information System 5. Consultation and Complaints 6. Service Innovation</p>	Likert Scale 1 – 5
<p>6. Human Resources Competence and Professionalism (X5) According to Spencer and Spencer, competence is defined as a fundamental characteristic that is inherent in an individual and directly influences success in carrying out a job or facing certain situations with superior performance. Meanwhile, Siagian explained that professionalism reflects the ability to carry out tasks effectively, produce high-quality output, be timely, accurate, and follow systematic procedures that are easy for service users to understand.</p>	<p>1. Self-development 2. Loyalty or faithfulness 3. Punctuality 4. Ability 5. Initiative</p>	Likert Scale 1 – 5

Source: Journals

4. Multiple Regression Analysis

In this study, hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis processed using Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) software. The multiple linear regression method is used to determine the extent to which independent variables influence the dependent variable. The general form of the multiple linear regression equation used in this study is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

Where:

Y	=	Dependent Variable, Quality of Public Services
α	=	Intercept Constant
X1	=	Independent Variable, Budget Availability
X2	=	Independent Variable, Technology
X3	=	Control Variables, Infrastructure
X4	=	Control Variables, Policy Changes and Regulations
X5	=	Control Variables, Competence and Professionalism of Human Resources
$\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \beta_4 \beta_5$	=	Regression Coefficient
e	=	Term Error

V. RESEARCH DISCUSSION

a. Overview of Research Location

The Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall (MPP) was established based on the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Public Service Malls. In this decree, Bukittinggi City is one of the regions designated to immediately establish an MPP. The main objective of establishing the Bukittinggi City MPP is to provide services to the public by prioritizing the principles of speed, convenience, affordability, security, and comfort, as well as encouraging increased national competitiveness.

Institutionally, the management of the Public Service Mall (MPP) is under the direct responsibility of the Head of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services (PMPTSP) Service, as stipulated in Bukittinggi City Regional Regulation Number 41 of 2022 and

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Bukittinggi Mayor Regulation Number 41 of 2022 concerning the Position, Organizational Structure, Duties and Functions, and Work Procedures of the PMPTSP Service. The PMPTSP Service is a public service unit within the Bukittinggi City Government, which has the main task of administering government affairs in the field of investment and one-stop integrated services. This agency is led by a Head of Service who is directly responsible to the Mayor through the Regional Secretary. The organizational structure of the Bukittinggi City PMPTSP Service is classified as a type C service, consisting of one secretariat and two coordinators.

b. Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

The next step in this research is to describe each variable, both independent and dependent variables, which are presented in the form of a frequency distribution. The independent variables in this study include: budget availability (X1), technology utilization (X2), infrastructure conditions (X3), policy and regulatory dynamics (X4), and human resource competence and professionalism (X5). Meanwhile, the dependent variable is the quality of public services (Y). The description of each variable is presented based on the Respondent Achievement Level (TCR) value.

c. Quality of Public Services (Y)

The assessment of public service quality in this study is based on the perceptions of the public and employees who use services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. A total of 150 respondents participated, representing the predetermined sample size. Information related to this variable is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Public Service Quality Variable (Y)

No	Score										Sam pel	Avera ge	TCR	Information
	SS		S		RR		TS		STS					
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%				
1	75	50.	75	50.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.50	90	Very good
2	50	33.	89	59.	11	7.3	-	-	-	-	150	4.26	85.2	Good
3	65	43.	85	56.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.43	88.6	Good
4	74	49.	76	50.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.49	89.8	Good
5	52	34.	98	65.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.34	86.8	Good
6	78	52.	72	48.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.52	90.4	Very good
7	72	48.	78	52.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.48	89.6	Good
8	70	46.	80	53.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.46	89.2	Good
9	59	39.	91	60.	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	4.39	87.8	Good
10	49	32.	98	65.	3	2.0	-	-	-	-	150	4.30	86	Good
Average												4.41	88.34	Good

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing in 2025

Referring to Table 3, the average score for the Public Service Quality variable provided by the public and employees using services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall was 4.41, with a Respondent Achievement Rate (TCR) of 88.34%. This finding indicates that respondents rated the quality of public services as good.

d. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the extent to which budget availability, technology, infrastructure, policy and regulatory changes, and human resource competency and professionalism influence the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. Furthermore, this analysis aims to test the hypotheses established in the study. The regression model was constructed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach, which allows for the assessment of the contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable. The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 4.21 below.

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant)	10,312	2,672		3,860	.000
Budget Availability (X1)	.142	.071	.132	1,996	.048
Technology (X2)	.400	.067	.417	5,982	.000
Infrastructure (X3)	.164	.069	.266	2,394	.018
Policy and Regulation (X4)	.091	.085	.125	2,076	.024
Human Resource Competence and Professionalism (X5)	.171	.179	.101	2,014	.019

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services (Y)

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2025

Next, the regression coefficient values of each variable are entered into the multiple linear regression equation, which can be written as follows:

$$Y = 10.312 + 0.142 X1 + 0.400 X2 + 0.164 X3 + 0.091 X4 + 0.171 X5$$

Based on the regression equation, the constant value of 10.312 indicates that if all independent variables—namely budget availability, technology, infrastructure, policy and regulatory changes, and human resource competence and professionalism—are zero, then the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall remains at 10.312 units, assuming other variables are in a constant condition.

The regression coefficient for the budget availability variable (X1) of 0.142 indicates a positive effect on the quality of public services. This means that every Rp1.00 increase in budget availability will result in a 0.142 unit increase in the quality of public services, assuming the other variables remain unchanged.

Furthermore, the technology variable's regression coefficient (X2), which is 0.400, also indicates a positive effect. This means that every one-unit increase in technology utilization will increase the quality of public services by 0.400 units, if other variables remain constant.

For the infrastructure variable (X3), the coefficient value of 0.164 indicates that an increase in infrastructure by one unit will contribute to an increase in the quality of public services by 0.164 units, assuming that other variables do not change.

The regression coefficient for the policy and regulatory change variable (X4) was recorded at 0.091, also reflecting a positive influence. This means that every one-unit increase in this aspect will increase the quality of public services by 0.091 units, provided that other variables remain constant.

Finally, for the variable of human resource competence and professionalism (X5), the regression coefficient of 0.171 indicates that a one unit increase in this variable will increase the quality of public services by 0.171 units, assuming all other variables remain constant.

e. Hypothesis Testing (T-Test)

Based on the results of partial hypothesis testing shown in Table 4.21, all independent variables were proven to have a significant influence on the dependent variable, namely the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

For the budget availability variable (X1), the calculated t value was 1.996, which was greater than the t table of 1.986, with a significance value of 0.048 (<0.05). This indicates that budget availability has a positive and significant effect on the quality of public services, so the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.

Furthermore, the technology variable (X2) shows a t-count of 5.982, which far exceeds the t-table value of 1.986, as well as a significance value of 0.000. This means that the use of technology significantly contributes positively to the quality of public services, and the related hypothesis can be accepted. For the infrastructure variable (X3), the t-count value of 2.394 with a significance of 0.018 (<0.05) indicates that infrastructure has a positive and significant influence on the quality of public services. Thus, the hypothesis regarding this variable is accepted. For the policy and regulatory change variable (X4), the t-count of 2.076 and a significance value of 0.024 indicate that this variable also has a significant influence on the quality of public services, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Finally, the variable of human resource competence and professionalism (X5) has a t-test of 2.014 and a significance value of 0.019. Because this value is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that this variable has a positive and significant effect on the quality of public services, and the proposed hypothesis is accepted. Overall, the results of the t-test prove that all independent variables in this regression model have a positive and significant effect on the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

f. F Test (Concurrent Hypothesis Testing)

To determine the influence of independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable, the F test is used. The results of the simultaneous regression analysis are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Simultaneous F-Test Results

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1.204.276	5	240.855	48.595	.000 ^a
Residual	713.724	144	4.956		
Total	1.918.000	149			

a. Predictors: (Constant), HR KP (X5), Budget Availability (X1), Technology (X2), Infrastructure (X3), PK and Regulation (X4)

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing in 2025

Based on the results of the F significance test listed in Table 5, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained. Because this value is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, it can be concluded that the regression model used is valid for predicting the dependent variable, namely the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. This means that the variables of budget availability, technology, infrastructure, changes in policies and regulations, and human resource competence and professionalism simultaneously have a significant effect on the quality of public services. Thus, the hypothesis stating that all independent variables together have a significant influence on the quality of public services is accepted.

g. Determinant Coefficient

The coefficient of determination is used to measure the overall contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable in the model being studied. The coefficient of determination values can be seen in Table 4.23 below.

Table 5

Determinant Coefficient Test

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.792a	.628	.615	22630	1,822

a. Predictors: (Constant), HR KP (X5), Budget Availability (X1), Technology (X2), Infrastructure (X3), PK and Regulation (X4)

b. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services (Y)

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing in 2025

The coefficient of determination test results show that the R² value is 0.628. This means that the variables of budget availability, technology, infrastructure, policy and regulatory changes, and human resource competence and professionalism together contribute 62.8% to the variation in public service quality at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall. Meanwhile, the remaining 37.2 % is influenced by other variables outside this research model.

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

VI. CLOSING

a. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussions involving 150 respondents, consisting of the public and employees who use services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Budget availability has a positive and significant impact on the quality of public services. This indicates that the more adequate the available budget allocation, the higher the quality of services provided to the public.
2. Technology has been proven to have a positive and significant impact on the quality of public services. Appropriate and optimal use of technology can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of service processes at Public Service Malls.
3. Infrastructure also has a positive and significant impact on the quality of public services. The availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure supports the creation of convenient, fast, and high-quality services.
4. Changes in policy and regulations have a positive and significant impact on the quality of public services. Flexible policies and supportive regulations can create a more responsive and accountable service system.
5. The competence and professionalism of human resources have a positive and significant impact on the quality of public services. Employees with professional skills and attitudes are key factors in achieving optimal public services.
6. Simultaneously, the five independent variables—budget availability, technology, infrastructure, policy and regulatory changes, and human resource competence and professionalism—together provide a positive and significant contribution to the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall.

b. Suggestion

Based on the limitations faced and the findings obtained in this study, the researcher provides several suggestions which are expected to be material for consideration by related parties:

1. **Budget Availability**
Although the budget availability to support the quality of public services at the Bukittinggi City Public Service Mall has been assessed as very good, improvements still need to be made, particularly in the aspect of financial management training. Improving the capacity of human resources in managing budgets effectively and efficiently will further strengthen the utilization of the available budget. The results of the study indicate that the item "Financial management training is provided periodically to HR" received the lowest score from respondents. Given the complexity of financial management, training should be implemented periodically and in stages to make it easier for HR to understand, rather than being conducted in one dense session.
2. **Technology:**
In general, the use of technology has received a positive response. However, there are still challenges in the use of service systems, particularly in the item "Public service applications or systems are easy for the public to use," which received a less than optimal score. This indicates the need to increase the intensity of public outreach on application use to ensure technology can be utilized effectively and equitably.
3. **Infrastructure:**
The available infrastructure has been deemed adequate to support public services. However, respondents assessed that there are still shortcomings in the aspect of "Directional information and instructions for using facilities are clearly available on-site." Improvements in the quality of visual information and direct support from staff in providing guidance on using facilities are needed, given that not all residents are able to understand the available instructions.
4. **Policy and Regulatory Changes**
Policy and regulatory changes have been assessed as quite good, but still need improvement in the aspect of "Policy changes strengthen public complaint handling mechanisms." A low score on this indicator indicates a lack of public understanding of the policy changes. Therefore, more effective and comprehensive outreach is essential whenever a policy change occurs.
5. **Human Resources Competence and Professionalism**
While human resources competence and professionalism have been assessed as good, organizational support for improving human resources capacity still needs to be strengthened. Specifically, regarding the item "The organization supports the continuous improvement of human resources competence," formal policies are needed, such as the issuance of decrees (SK) that support employees in developing their competencies. This is crucial to eliminate structural barriers to improving human resources quality.
6. **Recommendations for Further Research:**

Analysis of Determinants of Public Service Quality at Public Service Malls in Bukittinggi City

Future research is expected to expand the analytical model used by adding other variables that could potentially influence the quality of public services. Future researchers are advised to consider using different methodological approaches, expanding the number of respondents, and selecting a variety of research locations. These steps aim to obtain more comprehensive findings and increase the generalizability of the research results.

REFERENCES

- 1) Alim, Muhammad Nur, Muhammad Tahir Haning, and Syahribulan Syahribulan. 2020. "Electronic Claim Innovation for Old Age Security at the Makassar Branch Office of BPJS Employment." *JAKPP (Journal of Policy Analysis & Public Services)* : 1–14. doi:10.31947/jakpp.v6i1.8558.
- 2) Arifin Akbar. 2018. "Analysis of Factors Influencing the Quality of Public Services at the Medan Sunggal District Office, Medan City." *Journal* .
- 3) Arikunto. 2016. "Teaching Speaking At Senior High School Number 1 Muaro Jambi Regency." (1): 1–13.
- 4) Bambang Suprianto. 2023. "Literature Review: Application of Information Technology in Improving the Quality of Public Services." *Journal of Government and Politics* 8(2): 123–28. doi:10.36982/jpg.v8i2.3015.
- 5) Chaichinarat, Pichaiapat, Thanin Ratanaolarn, Krissana Kiddee, and Paitoon Pimdee. 2018. "Thailand's automotive service quality customer satisfaction: A servqual model cfa of suzuki mo." *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review* 18(2): 99–113. doi:10.59588/2350-8329.1168.
- 6) Dinda Septiani, Maya Arieska, and Lisa Sulistyawati. 2022. "Business Development Strategy Using Product Life Cycle (PLC) Method and Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix." *Reslaj: Religion Education Social Laa Roiba Journal* 4(6): 1532–50. doi:10.47467/reslaj.v4i6.1171.
- 7) Emilia, Khairunnisa. 2021. "Factors Influencing the Quality of Public Services at the Cintapuri District Office, Banjar Regency." *Public Administration* 2(1): 1–79.
- 8) Ghozali. 2018. "Source: www.idx.co.id data processed." 52(4): 33–43.
- 9) Hadi, Prayoga Luthfil, Tilaka Wasanta, and Wimpy Santosa. 2021. "The Effect of Road Infrastructure Index on Economic Indicators in Indonesia." *HPJI Journal* 7(2): 143–52. doi:10.26593/jhpji.v7i2.5058.143-152.
- 10) Handayani. 2020. "Chapter III Research Methods." *Suparyanto and Rosad (2015* 5(3): 248–53.
- 11) Hawing, Hardianto, and Nursaleh Hartaman. 2021. "Money Politics in Indonesian Democracy." *Journal of Social Politics and Governance (JSPG)* 3(1): 45–53. doi:10.24076/jspg.v3i1.533.
- 12) Herlinda. 2016. "The Influence of Information Technology on Improving the Quality of Public Services at PT Pos Indonesia in Tanah Grogot District." *eJournal of Government Science* 4(1): 306–18.
- 13) Hooper, Daire, Joseph Coughlan, and Michael R. Mullen. 2008. "Structural equation modeling: Guidelines for determining model fit." *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods* 6(1): 53–60.
- 14) Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63. 2003. "Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment No. 63 of 2003 Concerning General Guidelines for Public Services."
- 15) Mahmudi. 2015. "(Study on Batu City Government)."
- 16) Mursidah, Lailul Public Service Management Textbook. 2020. *Textbook* .
- 17) Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23. 2017. "Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Public Service Malls." 2017 53(9): 1689–99.
- 18) Government Regulation Number 5. 2021. "STATE GAZETTE." (15).
- 19) Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 89. 2021. "Presidential Regulation Number 89 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Public Service Malls." *Presidential Regulation Number 89 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Public Service Malls* (097575): 1–11.
- 20) Ramdani, Ari. 2020. "Changes in Public Service Quality & Train User Satisfaction in Tasikmalaya City." *Scientific Journal of Administrative Sciences* 9(2): 1–8. doi:10.33592/jjia.v10i1.503.
- 21) Renyut, Selvia F G. 2023. "Public Perception of the Quality of Public Services." *Mirai Management Journal* 8(1): 540–54.
- 22) Sugiyono. 2013. *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods* .
- 23) State Administration System of the Republic of Indonesia. 2004. "State Administration System of the Republic of Indonesia (SANKRI) Book III." *Book 3*.
- 24) Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25. 2009. *LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA NUMBER 25 OF 2009* . www.bphn.go.id.